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Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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Interdisciplinary approaches for examining individual sensitivity to radiotherapy and inflammatory mediators

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Radiotherapy is a widely used anticancer treatment, often used in combination with surgery and chemotherapy. One of the challenges of radiation oncology in the era of personalized medicine is the identification of biomarkers associated with individual radiosensitivity. Understanding the complex relationship between radiation therapy, inflammation and the immune response in malignant diseases opens new avenues for research and radiation therapy, in order to optimize and personalize the treatment for each patient. A growing number of data suggests that exist a direct link by which radiation stimulates the immune system, which in turn contributes to the death of tumor cells. Radiotherapy has a significant impact on the modulation of the immune system through the activation of cytokine cascades. The balance between pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokines is critical in determining positive or negative outcome, adverse reactions and resistance to radiation therapy.

Several studies evaluate the possible clinical value of the associations between clinical, physical, and biological factors, and risk for development of acute radiotoxicity in patients with prostate cancer.

Analysis of circulating cytokine levels during radiotherapy showed that increased serum concentrations of IL-6 were significantly associated with higher grade of acute genitourinary toxicity.

The prediction of individual radiosensitivity might be based on determination of cytokine levels changes at specific time during course of radiotherapy which is only a part of the complex multifactorial puzzle influencing the radiotoxicity.

Keywords: cancer, cytokine, immunology, IL-6

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